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PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL FACE PACK

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to formulate and evaluate a cosmetic herbal face pack for all type skin by using natural ingredients with the varying concentrations, Three different formulations containing ingredients such as Mint , Methi , Green tea, multani mitti, White sandal wood, orange peel procured from the local market were prepared named as F1 , F2 & F3, then passed through sieve no 44 mixed geometrically and evaluated for its organoleptic and physio-chemical, general powder and chemical evaluation. The dried powder of combined form had passable flow property which is suitable for a face pack. All prepared formulations were evaluated by different parameters like organoleptic properties and physio-chemical parameters and stability along with irritancy test & photo irritation. Herbal face packs or masks are used to stimulate blood circulation, rejuvenates the muscles and help to maintain the elasticity of the skin and remove dirt from skin pores. In this study it is concluded that all the formulations of face packs found to be good in physical parameters, free from skin irritations so we found good properties for the face packs and further optimization studies are required on this study to find the useful benefits of face packs on human use as cosmetic product.

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INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are commercially available products that are used to improve the appearance of the skin by action of cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness. From the ancient time, different herbs are used for cleaning, beautifying and to manage them. Face skin is the major part of the body, which indicates the health of an individual [1] [2]. It consists of materials such as amino acids, lipids and carbohydrates etc. So that a balanced nutrition is required for the skin to keep it clear glossy and healthy. [3] In ayurveda, the herbal paste is called as “mukha lepa” used for as a facial therapy. This herbal paste smeared on face to treat acne, pimple, scars, marks and pigments. [4] Face pack is the smooth powder which is used for facial application. These preparations are applied on the face in the form of liquid or pastes and allowed to dry and set to form film giving tightening, strengthening and cleansing effect to the skin. [5] They are usually left on the skin for ten to twenty five minutes to allow all the water to evaporate, the resulting film thus contracts and hardens and can easily be removed. The warmth and tightening effect produced by application of face pack produces the stimulating sensation of a rejuvenated face, while the colloidal and adsorption clays used in these preparations remove the dirt and grease from the skin of the face. When the applied face pack is eventually removed skin debris and deposited dirt gets removed with it. Face packs are basically additives delivering some additional benefits. Different types of herbal face packs are used for different types of skin. Herbal face packs are helps to reduce wrinkles, pimples, acne and dark circles. Also increase the fairness and smoothness of skin. It also helps someone to boost their confidence. Ayurveda is the most useful and successful means for achieving this purpose [6] these packs are available in various types and forms and broadly classified into the following categories: [7]

1. Plastic masks: Wax based, latex based, or vinyl based
2. Hydrocolloid masks: Gel masks (ready to use)
3. Argillaceous masks: Clay based or earth based (ready to use or dry powder) [8]

Present research article deals with the formulation and evaluation of cosmetic herbal face pack by using natural materials i.e Mint, Methi, Green tea, multani mitti, White sandal wood, orange peel. The main objective of this study was made to formulate face packs of different natural ingredients like Mint for cleansers, astringents. Methi for antiaging and effect repair damage skin. green tea for age spots and wrinkles. Multani mitti for soothes the skin and glowing skin. sandal wood for cure sun burn and cure pimples orange peel for its anti-acne, removing tan and the formulations were evaluated for Physical parameters like Color, Odor, pH, Consistency and Feel and irritancy test, photo irritancy test (Presence of sun) and Stability studies for one month.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Table 1: List of materials used in formulation of face pack.

Sr. No.	Plant name	Medicinal use	Figure
1	Mint (<i>Mentha piperata</i>)	Used in cleansers, astringents toners and moisturizers treat acne, brightens hydrates your skin get rid of black heads diminishes under eye dark circle.	
2	Green Tea <i>Camellia sinensis</i> L. <i>Theaceae</i>	Many scientists believe that free radicals contribute to the aging process as well as the development of a number of health problems. Polyphenols present in green tea helps in anti-ageing. Makes your skin looks younger and better.	
3	Methi (<i>TrigonElla foenum guaiacum</i>)	Repair damaged skin hydration on your skin cure acne moistures skin, anti-aging effect	
4	Orange peel (<i>Citrus limon</i>)	It cures blackheads, cell buildup around the pores brightness your face, dark circles, dry skin, removing tan.	
5	Safed chandan (<i>Santalum album</i>)	Amazingly to cure, sun burn to cure, pimples, clean flawless healthy glowing skin.	

6	Multani mitti (Fuellers earth)	Remove all the impurities and dead skin cells multani mitti will help to make you skin radiant and excellent for irritate skin, soothes the skin fresh radiant and glowing skin.	
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All the natural materials used in the present study i.e., Mint , Methi , Green tea, multani mitti, White sandal wood, orange peel were purchased from local market (Dehradun), in a form of dried powder The details of the plant material used for the formulation of face pack are mentioned in Table 1.[9] [10]

Formulation of herbal face pack- Preparation-

Three different formulations were prepared with varying concentrations of all ingredients named as F1 to F3. Concentration of each ingredient was mentioned in Table 2. The accurate quantity ingredients were weighed and ground into fine powder by using sieve # 44. Then the all ingredients were mixed geometrically by serial dilution method for uniform mixing. Then the prepared face pack was packed into a self- sealable polyethylene bag, labeled and used for further studies.

Table 2: Composition of Herbal Face Pack.

Sr. no	Ingredients name	F1 (gm)	F2(gm)	F3(gm)
1	Mint	15	20	18
2	Methi	12	10	9
3	Safed chandan	30	32	28
4	Orange peel	10	4	6
5	Green tea	5	4	3
6	Multani mitti	28	30	36

Procedure of Face Pack Application

Take prepared face pack powder in a bowl as per the requirement and add rose water to mix. Mix well and apply over the facial skin. Cover the acne and blemishes spots too. Kept as it is for complete drying for 20 to 25 min and then wash with cold water

Methods of Evaluation

Following evaluation parameters were performed to ensure superiority of prepared face pack;

Organoleptic Evaluation

The organoleptic parameters include its Appearance, color, odor, Texture, & Nature of face pack after wash (Table: 3) which were evaluated manually for its physical properties.

Table 3: Organoleptic Properties.

Sr.No.	Parameters	Observations		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Appearance	Powder (free flowing)	Powder (free flowing)	Powder (free flowing)
2	color	Slight yellow	Slight yellow	Slight yellow
3	Odor	slight	slight	Slight
4	texture	fine	fine	Fine
6	Nature of face powder after wash	soft and fresh clean from dirt	soft and fresh clean from dirt	soft and fresh clean from dirt

Physical Evaluation

The particle size was tested by microscopy method. The flow property of the dried powder of combined form was evaluated by performing Tapped density Bulk density Angle of Repose by funnel method, Hausner's ratio Carr's index Grittiness. (Table: 4).

Table 4: Physical evaluation.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Observations		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Tapped density	3 gm/ml	2.6 gm/ml	2.9 gm/ml
2	Bulk density	10 gm/ml	10 gm/ml	10 gm/ml
3	Angle of repose	1.125 ⁰	1.075 ⁰	1.047 ⁰
4	Hausner's ratio	3.3	3.8	3.4
5	Carr's index	70	74	71
6	Grittiness	No gritty particles were found when mixed with water	No gritty particles were found when mixed with water	No gritty particles were found when mixed with water

Physicochemical Evaluation

Total Ash content & acid insoluble ash was performed using Muffle furnace, pH was found by using pH meter and loss on drying & Flavonoid test (Shinoda test, alkaline reagent test, Lead acetate test, Ferric chloride test) was also performed.

Table 5: Physicochemical Evaluation.

S.No.	Parameters	Observations		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Ash value (gm)	73	36.5	43
2	PH	7.1	7.2	7.2
3	Loss on drying(gm)	42	45	50
4	Acid insoluble ash(gm)	1.16	1.81	1.61
5	Flavonoid Test	Presence of Flavonoid	Presence of Flavonoid	Presence of Flavonoid

Irritancy test

Mark an area on hands. Definite quantities of prepared face packs were applied to the specified area and time was noted. Irritancy, Redness, Swelling was checked for regular intervals up to 24 hrs and reported. The Photo-irritation (Presence of sun) was checked regular interval of 15 min.

Table 6: Irritancy test.

Sr.No.	Parameters	Observations		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Irritation	NIL	NIL	NIL
2	Redness	NIL	NIL	NIL
3	Swelling	NIL	NIL	NIL
4	Photo-irritation (Presence of sun)	No Irritation No redness No swelling	No Irritation No redness No swelling	No Irritation No redness No swelling

Figure : 1 Before.

Figure : 2 After.

Irritancy test

Figure:4 Before.

Figure:5 After.

Photo Irritation (Presence of sun).**Stability studies**

Stability testing of prepared formulation was conducted for formulations by storing at different temperature conditions for the period of one month. The packed glass vials of formulation stored at different temperature conditions viz., Room temperature and 40°C and were evaluated for physical parameters like Color, Odor, pH, Texture and Smoothness.

Table 7: Evaluation of stability studies of formulation at Room Temperature.

Sr.No.	Parameters	Room Temperature (Observations)		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Color	No change	No change	No change
2	Odour	No change	No change	No change
3	pH	7.1	7.2	7.2
4	Texture	fine	Fine	Fine
5	Smoothness	smooth	Smooth	Smooth

Table 8: Evaluation of stability studies of formulation at Oven Temperature (40°C).

Sr.No.	Parameters	OvenTemperature (40°C)		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Color	Change (slight yellow to dark)	Change (slight yellow to dark)	Change (slight yellow to dark)
2	Odour	No change	No change	No change
3	pH	6.2	6.3	6.2
4	Texture	fine	Fine	Fine
5	Smoothness	smooth	smooth	Smooth

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical parameters:

The different formulation of face pack was prepared and evaluated for physical parameters showed in the Table 3, & Table 4. The flow property parameter showed free flowing properties. The colors of formulations were different due to variation in composition of contents. The odor of prepared formulations was good acceptable which is desirable as cosmetic formulations. The pH of all formulations lied near to neutral range i.e. in the range of 6 to 7 pH. (Figure 2). The ash content and moisture content were within limit (Table 5).

Irritancy test

The results of irritancy test were shown in Table 6. This formulation is safe to use for skin.

Stability studies

The stability studies showed a slight change in color, pH of formulation which was stored at 40°C and no changes were observed at room temperature (Table 7, Table 8).

CONCLUSION

Natural remedies are more acceptable in the belief that they are safer with fewer side effects than the synthetic ones. Natural remedies are more acceptable in the belief that they are safer with side effects than they synthetic ones.

Herbal face pack or masks are used to stimulate blood circulation rejuvenates the muscles and help to maintain the elasticity of the skin and remove dirt from skin pores the advantage of herbal cosmetics is their non-toxic nature reduce the allergic reactions and time tested usefulness of may ingredients thus in the present work we found good properties for the face packs and in future further optimization studies are required on this study to find the useful benefits of face pack on human use as cosmetic products.

Abbreviations:

Gm = Gram
°C = Degree Celsius

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Conflict of Interest

The authors do not report any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Okereke JN, Udebuani AC, Ezeji EU, Obasi KO, Nnoli MC. Possible Health Implications Associated with Cosmetics: A Review, *Sci J Public Health* 2015; 3(5-1): 58-63.
2. Mary P. Lupo. Antioxidants and Vitamins in Cosmetics. *Clin Dermatol* 2001; 19: 467–473.
3. Sowmya KV, Darsika CX, Grace F, Shanmuganathan S. Formulation & Evaluation of Poly-herbal Face wash gel. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2015; 4(6): 585-588.
4. Millikan, Larry E. Cosmetology, Cosmetics, Cosmeceuticals: Definitions and Regulations. *Clin Dermatol* 2001; 19 (4); 371-374.
5. Rieger MM. Harry's Cosmeticology. In: Chapter 23, Face, Body& Hair Masks & Scrubs. 8th ed. vol I. New York: Chemical Publishing Co., Inc.; 2009. p. 471-483.
6. Zinnia. Ayurvedic Face Packs for Glowing Skin. *Style Craze*, Feb 2017 [cited 2017 Apr 24]. Available from: <http://www.stylecraze.com/articles/5-ayurvedic-face-packsfor-glowing-skin>
7. A. fathima, sujithvarma, p. jagannath, m. Akash. General review on herbal cosmetics international journal of drug formulation and research. *Varma* volume 2 Issue 5, sep-oct.2011.
8. Laxmi s. joshi and harshal A panwar .herbal cosmetics and cosmeceuticals: An overview,joshi and panwarnat *prod chem Res*2015.
9. Sushil kumar, A. Akhila, A.A.Naqvi, A.K. Singh, et.al. "Medicine plants in skin care" 1-edition, 1994, central Institute of medicinal and Aromatic plants. Pg no.1-10.
10. Anupama Shukla, pankaj Kothari, AkhileshShukla, CR Yadav. An ayurvedic outlook to mukhalepa(face pack) for beauty care global J Res. Med. Plants &Indigen.Med.| Volume 5, Issue 6|june 2016.

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